

Supplement 2: Supplemental Analyses

Physical Activity Guideline Adherence and High-Impact Chronic Pain Among U.S. Adults: A Cross-Sectional Analysis of the 2020 National Health Interview Survey

S1. Missingness Comparison: Included vs. Excluded Respondents

Table S1 compares demographic characteristics and HICP status (where available) between respondents included in the analytic sample ($n = 27,068$) and those excluded due to missing data ($n = 4,500$). Excluded respondents were older, more likely to be female, and had substantially higher HICP prevalence (13.2% vs. 5.1%), suggesting that complete-case analysis may underestimate population HICP prevalence.

: Table S1. Unweighted comparison of included vs. excluded respondents.

Characteristic	level	Excluded	Included	p	test
n		4500	27068		
Age, mean (SD)		58.71 (17.01)	52.76 (18.23)	<0.001	
Sex (%)	Male	1985 (44.1)	12536 (46.3)	0.007	
	Female	2513 (55.9)	14532 (53.7)		
Race/Ethnicity (%)	NH White	3254 (72.3)	18836 (69.6)	<0.001	
	NH Black	532 (11.8)	2669 (9.9)		
	NH Asian	37 (0.8)	152 (0.6)		
	Hispanic	452 (10.0)	3381 (12.5)		
	NH Other/Multiracial	225 (5.0)	2030 (7.5)		
HICP status (%)	0	630 (86.8)	25676 (94.9)	<0.001	
	1	96 (13.2)	1392 (5.1)		

Note: HICP status available for 726 of 4,500 excluded respondents; the remaining lacked classifiable pain or activity-limitation data. P-values from chi-squared (categorical) or *t*-test (continuous).

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S2. Confounding Assessment: Model A vs. Model B

To assess potential confounding by health-related and socioeconomic factors, we estimated adjusted HICP prevalences under two models on the same expanded complete-case sample. Model A adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity only (total association). Model B additionally adjusted for education, BMI category, arthritis history, depression frequency, anxiety frequency, and income-to-poverty ratio (conservative association after additional adjustment). We note that several Model B covariates (BMI, arthritis, depression, anxiety) may lie on the causal pathway between PA and HICP; thus, Model B may represent overadjustment and should be interpreted as the lower bound of the true association.

: Table S2a. Adjusted HICP prevalence (%) by PA category, Models A and B.

PA category	Model A: Adj. HICP %	Model A: 95% CI	Model B: Adj. HICP %	Model B: 95% CI
No PA	8.4	7.3–9.6	12.8	11.3–14.2
Some PA but below guidelines	3.9	2.8–4.9	9.5	8.1–10.8
Meets aerobic only	2.9	1.9–4.0	9.1	7.8–10.5
Meets aerobic + strength	2.9	1.9–3.9	10.0	8.6–11.5

: Table S2b. Linear trend in HICP across PA categories, Models A and B.

Model	Per-category change (pp)	95% CI	Trend p-value
A (demographics)	-1.80	-2.07 to -1.53	< 0.001
B (fully adjusted)	-0.90	-1.17 to -0.63	< 0.001

Note: Model A: age + sex + race/ethnicity. Model B: Model A + education + BMI category + arthritis + depression frequency + anxiety frequency + income-to-poverty ratio. The per-category change attenuated by approximately 50% from Model A to Model B, but the linear trend remained highly significant ($p < 0.001$).

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S3. Sensitivity Analysis: Excluding Code 95 Respondents

NHIS frequency-per-week recode code 95 denotes respondents who reported being “unable to do” a given activity type. In the primary analysis, these respondents were assigned zero frequency (equivalent to code 94, “never”). Because inability to exercise may itself be caused by pain, this coding could inflate the observed PA–HICP association. To test this, we re-estimated the primary models after excluding all respondents with code 95 on any PA frequency variable (n = 204 removed; analytic n = 26,864).

: Table S3a. Adjusted HICP prevalence excluding code 95 respondents.

PA category	Adj. HICP % (no 95)	95% CI
No PA	8.5	7.4–9.7
Some PA but below guidelines	3.9	2.9–5.0
Meets aerobic only	2.9	1.9–4.0
Meets aerobic + strength	2.9	1.9–3.9

: Table S3b. Trend test excluding code 95 respondents.

Analysis	Per-category change (pp)	95% CI	Trend p-value	n removed	Analytic n
Excluding code 95	-1.85	-2.11 to -1.58	< 0.001	204	26,864

Note: Results are virtually identical to the primary analysis (per-category change -1.85 pp vs. -1.82 pp in primary; $p < 0.001$ in both). Excluding code 95 respondents does not materially affect the findings.

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S4. Subgroup Analyses: Effect Modification by Age, Sex, and Race/Ethnicity

We tested whether the PA–HICP association varied across demographic subgroups by fitting interaction terms (PA ordinal score \times subgroup) in survey-weighted linear probability models. Stratified per-category slopes are reported alongside formal interaction p -values.

: Table S4a. Stratified per-category change in HICP (pp) by subgroup.

Modifier	Subgroup	Per-category change (pp)	95% CI	p-value
Age group	18-39	-0.47	-0.78 to -0.16	0.003
Age group	40-64	-2.96	-3.45 to -2.47	< 0.001
Age group	65+	-2.97	-3.60 to -2.34	< 0.001
Sex	Male	-1.41	-1.76 to -1.06	< 0.001
Sex	Female	-2.26	-2.64 to -1.87	< 0.001
Race/Ethnicity	NH White	-2.18	-2.51 to -1.84	< 0.001
Race/Ethnicity	NH Black	-1.63	-2.48 to -0.77	< 0.001
Race/Ethnicity	NH Asian	-3.45	-6.41 to -0.48	0.028
Race/Ethnicity	Hispanic	-1.17	-1.75 to -0.59	< 0.001
Race/Ethnicity	NH Other/Multiracial	-0.76	-1.53 to 0.01	0.055

: Table S4b. Interaction test p-values.

Modifier	Interaction p
Age group	< 0.001
Sex	< 0.001
Race/Ethnicity	0.013

Note: All three interaction terms were statistically significant. The PA–HICP gradient was strongest among adults aged 40+ and among women. Among racial/ethnic groups, NH White and NH Asian adults showed the steepest gradients, though the NH Asian estimate had wide confidence intervals due to smaller sample size.

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S5. Linear Probability Model: Predicted Probability Bounds

A known limitation of the linear probability model (LPM) is that predicted probabilities can fall outside $[0, 1]$. We examined the distribution of fitted values from the primary LPM.

: Table S5. LPM predicted probability diagnostics.

Metric	Value
Min predicted probability	-0.0265
Max predicted probability	0.1417
N predictions < 0	1533
N predictions > 1	0
Proportion in $[0,1]$	0.9434

Note: 1,533 observations (5.7%) had predicted probabilities slightly below zero (minimum -0.027). No predictions exceeded 1.0. These out-of-range predictions are substantively negligible and are typical for LPMs applied to low-prevalence outcomes. The modified Poisson model, which constrains predictions to the positive real line, serves as a complementary robustness check.

S6. Natural Cubic Spline Knot Placement

The dose-response model used a natural cubic spline via `ns(df = 3)` from the `splines` package for moderate-equivalent minutes/week (capped at 1,500). With `df = 3`, `ns()` places two internal knots at the 33rd and 67th percentiles of the observed data distribution.

: Table S6. Natural cubic spline knot locations from `ns(df = 3)`.

Knot type	Location (moderate-eq. min/wk)
Boundary (lower)	0
Internal (33rd percentile)	50
Internal (67th percentile)	270
Boundary (upper)	1,500

Note: Internal knots at 50 and 270 min/wk correspond to the 33rd and 67th percentiles of capped moderate-equivalent minutes/week among the analytic sample. Boundary knots are placed at the range extremes (0 and 1,500 min/wk).

S7. Justification for Capping Moderate-Equivalent Minutes at 1,500 Min/Week

Self-reported PA data can include implausibly high values. We capped moderate-equivalent minutes/week at 1,500 to reduce the influence of extreme observations on the spline-based dose-response model.

: Table S7. Distribution of extreme PA values.

Metric	Value
Total with valid moderate-eq. min/wk	27,068
Maximum (min/wk)	15,960
99th percentile (min/wk)	2100.0
99.5th percentile (min/wk)	2870.0

N > 1,000 min/wk	1,316
% > 1,000 min/wk	4.86%
N > 1,500 min/wk	536
% > 1,500 min/wk	1.98%

Note: The maximum observed value (15,960 min/wk) is implausible, equating to ~38 hours/day of moderate activity. The 99th percentile was 2100.0 min/wk. Capping at 1,500 min/wk (21.4 hr/wk, or ~3 hr/day) affected 536 respondents (1.98%) and represents a conservative threshold that retains high-but-plausible values while excluding reporting errors.

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S8. Prevalence Ratios: Models A and B

Prevalence ratios (PR) were estimated using survey-weighted modified Poisson regression (quasipoisson family, log link) following Zou (2004). PRs are a commonly used effect measure for cross-sectional studies with binary outcomes.

: Table S8a. Prevalence ratios for HICP by PA category — Model A (demographics).

PA category	PR	95% CI
No PA (ref)	1.00	ref
Some PA but below guidelines	0.45	0.38–0.54
Meets aerobic only	0.33	0.26–0.41
Meets aerobic + strength	0.26	0.20–0.34

: Table S8b. Prevalence ratios for HICP by PA category — Model B (fully adjusted).

PA category	PR	95% CI
No PA (ref)	1.00	ref
Some PA but below guidelines	0.59	0.50–0.69
Meets aerobic only	0.52	0.41–0.66
Meets aerobic + strength	0.50	0.39–0.66

Note: Model A: age + sex + race/ethnicity. Model B: Model A + education + BMI category + arthritis + depression frequency + anxiety frequency + income-to-poverty ratio. In Model A, adults meeting both aerobic and strength guidelines had 74% lower HICP prevalence compared to inactive adults (PR = 0.26). In Model B, this attenuation yielded a 50% lower prevalence (PR = 0.50), consistent with partial confounding by health-related covariates.

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